

FACTSHEET ON THE POLITICS OF INTEGRATION AND INCLUSION

MATILDE DELIVERABLE 6.1

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- H2020-EU.3.6.1.1. The mechanisms to promote smart, sustainable and inclusive growth
- H2020-EU.3.6.1.2. Trusted organisations, practices, services and policies that are necessary to build resilient, inclusive, participatory, open and creative societies in Europe, in particular taking into account migration, integration and demographic change

Deliverable 6.1 – Factsheet on the Politics of Integration and Inclusion

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Introduction

According to the MATILDE Grant Agreement (Nr. 870831), the aim of the “Factsheet of the politics of integration and inclusion” is to review and give an overview of existing political strategies, goals and programs (policies) related to coexistence and integration at the European level and in the ten MATILDE partner countries. The goals and guiding principles in the governance of migration and integration, considering their development across time in concomitance with key events from the 1990’s onward, will be highlighted.

Methodology

The Factsheet “Politics of Integration and Inclusion” is based on an in-depth literature review of political strategies and approved programs (policies) in the MATILDE countries and at the EU level, as well as of scientific studies and literature. The following outlined theories of coexistence and managing differences represent a selection and should illustrate the range of different approaches and understandings. The selected integration political goals, strategies, and programs (policies) of the EU and the MATILDE countries, as presented below, should provide an overview of the (country-specific) handling of international (third-country) migration and integration issues before and after the refugee crisis took place.

Understanding of integration and integration policies

”Integration’ as a chaotic concept: a word used by many but understood differently by most.“ (Robinson, 1998, 118 as cited by Ager & Strang, 2008, 167) In general, definitions or understandings of integration affect integration policies, and especially their targets. As a consequence, policies intend to influence integration processes. Understandings, policies and targets are interdependent

(Oliver & Gidley, 2015). Penninx and Garcés-Mascreñas (2016) mention, integration is often described in policies as a problem, which has to be solved, through integration policies. In order to understand integration policies, the following questions need to be answered: How is integration explained? How is immigration seen – as opportunity or as problem? Who is meant to be a legal immigrant? Who is defined as an unwanted or illegal migrant? Are immigrants described as foreigners, guests or members of the society? What can and shall be done to solve the problem of integration? Are immigrants ignored, treated like temporary guests or understood as permanent members of society? For whom are integration policies written? Which groups of migrants are included? Who is excluded?

Concept of coexistence and managing differences

Ager & Strang’s (2008) mid-level theory presents a model for analyzing integration from two perspectives: the view of migrants (in particular refugees) and the view of the respective local receiving society. In their theory, ten interdependent dimensions (employment, housing, education, health, social bridges, social bonds, social links, language and cultural knowledge, safety and stability, rights and citizenship) build a hierarchical pyramid, with the dimension “rights and citizenship” at its peak. This dimension serves as the basis and is the key for access to employment, housing, education and health care. These four dimensions are defined by Ager & Strang (2008) as “markers & means” of integration. In their theory, they identify three dimensions (social bridges, social bonds and social links) which build “social connection” and play an important role for the integration processes at a local level. The two dimensions “language and cultural knowledge” as well as “safety and stability” serve as “facilitators” to employment, housing, education and health (Ager & Strang, 2008; for further

details on the theory adopted to the MATILDE conceptual framework, see Kordel & Membretti, 2020, MATILDE Deliverable 2.4). As “spatial mobility” plays an important role for inclusion/exclusion especially in peripheral rural and mountain areas and can therefore be seen as a further facilitator, the model was expanded by this dimension (Weidinger et al., 2017; Weidinger, 2018).

Theories of coexistence may focus on factors such as how to deal with cultural differences or with the extent of equal opportunities and participation. According to John W. Berry et al. (2006), one outcome of the acculturation process, which “result[s] from the direct contact of groups or individuals from different cultures and which bring[s] about changes in the original cultural patterns of the individual or both cultures” (Redfield et al., 1936, 149, as cited by Kamhuber, 2019; own translation) could be **assimilation**. The term stems from the Latin “assimilo” and means to make something similar or equal. Processes of assimilation of individuals or groups to a host society/majority are multidimensional and comprise the cognitive (mental, consciousness) and emotional level, they are sense-focused (values), and strive for participation (equal opportunities) (Mintzel, 1997).

Arends-Tóth et al. (2004, 21) point out that in domain specific acculturation models (e.g. see Keefe & Padilla, 1987; Kim et al., 2001) “individual’s preference for adaptation and cultural maintenance may vary across life domains. [...] For example, one may seek economic or work assimilation and linguistic integration, while maintaining separation in family and marriage.”

The concept of **multiculturalism** refers to the socio-cultural characteristic of a society that several cultures coexist side by side, whether peacefully or in conflict, segregated or in togetherness. In contrast, multiculturalism describes a political program that reacts positively to the given fact of multiculturalism

(Mintzel, 1997). **Pluralism** is a key concept in the debate on multicultural societies. The concept originated in the USA and represented the counter concept to the Melting Pot Principle. “This pluralism also purposes One World, but One World in pluribus, as a federal union of diversities, not a diversion of diversities into undifferentiated unity.” (Kallen, 1956, 51-52).

Wolfgang Welsch (2005) considers recent worldwide social changes and integrates them in his model of **transculturality**. He points out that cultures are no longer homogenous, nor closed unities, but they are rather characterized by mixtures. Core of his concept is the idea of hybrid cultures showing interdependences, mixings and similarities. Cultures do not end at national borders, but transcend them, and elements of them can also be found in other cultures (Welsch, 2010).

While the above-mentioned theories focus more on dealing with cultural aspects of coexistence, the concept of **inclusion** deals with the question how diversity in groups or society is recognized. Inclusion is a designation originally used in the context of equality for people with disabilities, to enable them to live independently and be included in society (United Nations, 2008). If heterogeneity and diversity within a group is seen as an individual shortcoming, this can result in segregation and/or exclusion (Emanuelsson, 1998). Based on the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, the concept of inclusion transferred to people with migration experience, does not mean that individuals have to adapt to the mainstream (as it is required in the concept of integration), but the state ensures that all people can fully **participate** in common life (Praetor Intermedia, 2020). While “integration” could be fulfilled when a person finds a job (labour market integration), societal inclusion may not be achieved as long as the person has no realistic chance to participate in associations, sports clubs or community life.

Recent approaches, such as that of **social inclusion and belongingness**, which were further developed in the VOLPOWER project, focus on (similar) narratives of people, the need to find accessible environments (e.g. sports activities) for expressing one's own narrative and to foster social interaction between people sharing similar narratives. The underlying assumption is that sharing (similar/joint) narratives can result in a joint belongingness of newcomers and locals taking place in "narrative communities" (Korkut et al., 2020). The results of the RESPOND project show that "comprehensive, inconsistent or absent integration policies all lead to fraught belonging for European's refugees" (Rottmann, 2020).

A critical reflection of migration and the managing of its consequences is made possible by the **post-migrant discourse**. Post-migrant thinking opens up a "resistant stance against hegemonic social relations" (Hill & Yildiz, 2018, 7; own translation). A post-migrant analysis focuses on relations of inequality, calls for ending processes of exclusion, othering and racism (Foroutan, 2018) and invokes us to rethink migration as a social normality instead of a state of emergency (Hill & Yildiz, 2018).

Overall, it is important to mention that the "integration pathway not only depends on the characteristics of migrants themselves, but also on the reactions of the institutions and the population of the receiving society" (Bolt et al., 2010, 169).

Integration political goals and strategies at the European level

Before 1990

- 1985: Schengen Agreement on the elimination of border controls within the EU
- 1986: Council of Europe - Establishment of the Working Group on Integration

1990s

- 1990: Dublin Agreement on the responsibility for examining an asylum application lodged in the EU
- 1993: Maastricht Treaty as a first step towards European migration and asylum policy (regulates the entry and short-term stay of third-country nationals)
- 1999: Treaty of Amsterdam - Member States transfer competence of asylum, immigration and integration policy to the EU
- 1999: Tampere Programme (2000–2004) - Decision on necessary elements of an European immigration policy; the European Commission committed itself to the fair treatment of third-country nationals residing lawfully in the territory (for further details, see European Parliament, 1999)

2000s

- 2000: Communication from the Commission on a common immigration policy [COM(2000) 757 final]; economic and demographic development of the EU, the absorption capacity of the Member States, situation in the countries of origin, rights for third-country nationals, need for integration measures are outlined
- 2003: Communication from the Commission on Immigration, Integration and Employment [COM(2003) 336 final]; access to the EU labour market is seen as an essential prerequisite for a successful integration process
- 2004: Communication from the Commission - First Annual Report on Migration and Integration [COM(2004) 508 final]; "participation in the political decision-making process is an important formal step to granting foreigners similar rights and obligations as EU-nationals" (European Commission, 2004, 6)
- 2004: Hague Programme (2005–2009) - Ten priorities for the next five years; i.a. a common asylum area (harmonized procedure in accordance with the Union's values and humanitarian tradition) and maximising the positive impact of migration on EU's society and economy (for further details see, European Commission, 2005)
- 2005: Green Paper on an EU Approach to Managing Economic Migration [COM(2004) 811 final]
- 2005: Communication from the Commission - Policy Plan on Legal Migration [COM(2005) 669 final]
- 2005: Common framework for the integration of non-EU nationals [COM(2005) 389 final]
- 2007: Implementation of the European Integration Fund
- 2009: Stockholm Programme (2010–2014) - aiming i.a. to build a dynamic and comprehensive migration policy, focus on integration, unaccompanied minors, asylum - a common area of protection and sharing of responsibilities and solidarity between the Member States (for further details see, European Council, 2010)
- 2011: Implementation of the European Asylum Support Office, supporting the work towards a Common European Asylum System (EASO) (European Asylum Support Office, 2021)
- 2014: Post-Stockholm Programme (2015–2019) - existing priorities of the Stockholm Programme should be continued (e.g. Common European Asylum System) and focus on combating terrorism ("foreign fighters), unlawful migration, EU's external border management (for further details see, Demokratiezentrum Wien, 2016; Kramer, 2014)

2015

- 2015: European Commission's packages of measures to respond to the refugee crisis (for further details, see European Commission, 2015a and 2015b)
- 2015: Communication from the Commission – A European Agenda on Migration [COM(2015) 240 final]; reducing the incentives for irregular migration, saving lives and securing the external borders, a strong asylum policy and a new policy on legal migration (for further details, see European Commission, 2015c)
- 2015: Council of EU launched the EU naval operation (EUNAVFOR Med) against human smugglers and traffickers in the Mediterranean (for further details, see Council of the European Union, 2015)
- 2015: Eastern Mediterranean – Western Balkans route conference; aimed to enhance i.a. orderly management of refugee and migration flows
- 2015: Justice and Home Affairs Council – Actions to fight against xenophobia
- 2016: Launch of the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (FRONTEX)(for further details, see Council of the European Union, 2016a)
- 2016: Schengen Borders Code – Tightening controls at the EU's external borders (for further details, see Council of the European Union, 2016b)

Today

- 2018: Strengthening the possibilities of FRONTEX with regard to support Member States in return operations
- 2019: Visa policy: EU updated rules to facilitate legal travel and combat irregular migration (for further details, see Council of the European Union, 2019)
- 2019: Anchoring of migration policy in the Strategic Agenda 2019–2024 (for further details, see European Council, 2019)
- 2020: Communication from the Commission – Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion [COM(2020) 758 final]
- 2020: Communication from the Commission – New Pact on Migration and Asylum [COM(2020) 609 final] (For further information on the development of EU policies, see also König & Stadler, 2003; Gruber, 2010; Council of the European Union, 2020.)

Integration political goals and strategies on national level

The following chapter presents the different approaches of integration policies of the MATILDE countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and United Kingdom.

1. Austria

Immigration policy in Austria has been based on labour market strategies since the end of the Second World War (Biffl & Faustmann, 2013). Since the 1990s and especially after 2009, integration has become more institutionalized. Integration and asylum policies are quite restrictive and linked to labour market demands (Biffl, 2019).

2. Bulgaria

In Bulgaria, the number of migrants was very small for a long time. It increased with the accession to the European Union and the subsequent institutionalization of integration (EWSI, 2019). The Bulgarian integration approach could be summarized as very centralized and dominated by anti-migrant political discourse (Krsteva, 2019).

3. Finland

Integration in Finland is understood as a process including the whole society (Saukkonen, 2020). Integration policies are linked to the process of Europeanization of Finland (Puuronen, 2004) and aim to support, guide and help immigrants. Even though equality and positive social interaction are prioritized and multiculturalism is an aim (Hiitola et. al, 2018), racism and xenophobia are still present in the discourse.

4. Germany

Despite the fact that Germany is the third most popular country for international immigration in the world, the designation as a country of immigration is still officially denied (Eltges & Strubelt, 2019) and an overall integration approach is missing. German immigration policies tend to be more economically oriented. Nevertheless, migrants, who have to prove themselves on the labour market, are preselected and have to meet requirements concerning security and identity

(Schrammann, 2018). Integration policies, accordingly, follow the aspects of 'supporting' and 'demanding'.

5. Italy

The migration policies in Italy also prioritize economic and labour market needs. The legal residence of third-country nationals is linked to their regular working activity. Together with this utilitarian approach, a clear repressive and safety-oriented approach has defined irregular entry as a criminal offense. Safety and immigration are linked and effectiveness of judiciary and integration process are the main aims. As a result, third-country nationals become more marginalized and segregated.

6. Norway

Since the 1970s, Norway has become more heterogeneous and integration is understood as positive relation between migrants and the receiving society. Integration strategies are linked with multiculturalism and a pluralistic

understanding of Norway's society. Diverse cultural and religious ways of life are respected, protected and sustainably organized.

After a civic turn in debates on integration, migrants are now asked to meet requirements and fulfil conditions (Djuve, 2011). Integration is increasingly linked to conditions or 'demands' which is supposed to strengthen the preconditions for participation and inclusion. The Norwegian integration act aims to ensure the integration into society and the financial independence of migrants.

7. Spain

Spain does not have a defined integration model with shared responsibility of the national government and local entities or NGOs. Nevertheless, the Spanish integration policies focus on the needs of the labour market. The legal status of migrants is linked to their successful employment. After the economic crisis in 2008, the strategy failed, due to that fact the economic integration and sociocultural integration go along with each other in Spain (Moreno-Colom & De Alós, 2016).

8. Sweden

In Sweden, a ministry or authority focusing solely integration and a national strategy for integration do not exist. Instead, Sweden places a general emphasis on equality, obligation and possibilities independent of ethnic and cultural background. Sweden has a universal welfare system that aims to provide high-quality welfare services to all its citizens (Government of Sweden, 2017). In the late 1990s, the government set a goal and direction for the country's integration policy. There is a focus on the diversity of society and a societal development characterized by mutual respect and tolerance in which all, regardless of background, are involved in and co-responsible for. Sweden's approach is to involve the whole society in the integration process.

9. Turkey

Turkey has defined itself as homogenous. During the nation-building process in the 20th century, the nation was forced to homogenize and forced to be Turkish. Diversity was suppressed (Öniş, 2004). According to the Law on Foreigners and

International Protection, that was put into force in 2014, an intercultural model of integration is embraced by the Turkish state laying emphasis on the two-way nature of integration involving both locals and migrants. Despite having shortcomings in the political integration of migrants, access to citizenship and anti-discrimination laws, Turkey has recently performed relatively well in terms of the integration of migrants in general, and migrants under temporary protection in particular (MIPEX, 2020). The relative success of Turkey in the integration of migrants is also related to the engagement of local governments, NGOs and academia, which often underline the intercultural aspects of the integration of migrants.

10. United Kingdom

Integration policies of the United Kingdom have their seed in the 1960s, when they were designed to address migrants from New Commonwealth countries. Nowadays, the integration policies focus on migrants of the second generation as well as asylum seekers and refugees, but not third-country nationals or economic migrants. Concerning asylum policies, asylum seekers and refugees are divided into the categories “eligible for integration” and “not eligible for integration”. With the recognition of asylum, the integration process starts. According to Bloch (2008), employability is described as a key aspect of integration, while refugees have limited restricted access to the labour market.

Conclusion

Integration needs a multi-governance approach, coordinated at the local, regional, national, bilateral, and multilateral levels. The European Union on the highest multi-governance level has a limited influence on EU member states’ integration policies.

On the national level, the understandings of integration and the target groups of integration policies vary:

- Immigration policies in Austria are quite restrictive with the focus on labour market needs. Agreements of integration have to be signed by migrants; these agreements require a one-way process of integration with most responsibility placed on migrants.
- In Bulgaria, integration policies are based on European Union policies with a positive perception of migration. However, integration mostly works through bottom-up initiatives. But since 2015, the implementation of policies has stopped.
- Finland has a positive understanding of integration, describing it as a process involving the whole society and help and support for migrants.
- In Germany, a general integration approach does not exist, but different integration policies tend toward an economic orientation.
- Italy focuses on economic and labour market needs. Integration has to be effectively achieved through language learning and participation in economic, social and cultural life. In addition, immigration is linked to safety.
- For a long time, Norway approached multiculturalism, pluralistically with equal rights and opportunities for migrants – but more demands and

pressure have been laced on migrants in the recent years, for instance through mandatory introductory programs.

- In Spain, a general integration approach does not exist. Different policies focus on needs of the labour market, due to the belief that socio-cultural integration is achieved through economic integration.
- Sweden promotes equality independent of people's background and focuses on diversity. Nevertheless, newcomers have to attend a labour market program.
- After a long period of homogenization and exclusion of foreigners, Turkey now implements positive integration policies. The integration processes are successful due to bottom-up initiatives.
- The integration policies in the United Kingdom are directed at the second generation of migrants, asylum seekers and refugees, but not newcomers. In asylum policies, refugees are excluded from work and language learning is focused on instead.

A more detailed analysis of the presented integration political goals, strategies, and programs (policies) as well as perceptions of integration and inclusion on all governance levels with important changes since the 1990s is discussed in Deliverable D6.2 "Report on the existing integration-political goals, programmes and strategies".

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